

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Round 1) for **TEBT-2025-0011**

Submission information table

Submission Title	A Microinjection Approach to Evaluate Gap Junction Dynamics in 3D Multicellular Spheroids
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0011
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 editor (triage evaluation)
Submission Type	Method (General Methodology Paper) ▾
Preregistration Level	N/A (Not Applicable) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15660004
Report Number	1 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Editorial Review ▾
Evaluation Date	30 Jul 2025
Recommendation	Revise ▾

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This manuscript describes an approach to dye injection that the authors claim can improve the utility of 3D multicellular spheroids in cancer research, specifically in relation to analysing

cell-to-cell communication via gap junctions. In my opinion, this is a very promising first submission of a bench protocol manuscript. However, to be confident of a positive reception by peer-reviewers and minimise the number of rounds of reviewer comment, I am recommending the authors revise their manuscript before peer-review. In particular, I recommend the authors clarify and further develop the context and purpose of the methodology, making its specific contribution clearer. I also recommend adding a “discussion” section for issues that cannot readily be captured in the operational procedure that has been presented. I look forward to receiving the revised manuscript and, if everything goes to plan, later seeing reviewer comments on the method.

Checklist of minimum required information

P = Provided | R = Revisions recommended | X = Not Applicable

#	Status	Item checked
1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
2	<input type="radio"/>	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDiDs (if available) of each author are present
3	<input type="radio"/>	Correct institutional co-authorship + email to EiC if official publication of EBTC
4	<input type="radio"/>	Structured abstract has been provided
5	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
6	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Complete funding details are given, or “no funding” is declared
7	<input type="radio"/>	Informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided or disclosure declined
8	<input type="radio"/>	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
9	<input type="radio"/>	Data and code availability has been stated and links to both are functional
10	<input type="radio"/>	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
11	<input type="radio"/>	Supplemental materials have plain English file names
12	<input type="radio"/>	For Registered Reports submissions, preregistration level clearly indicated

Comments about minimum required information

#2 If feasible, adding ORCIDiDs to the preprint record helps with systems that automatically aggregate authors works into a single place, though it is not critical.

#4 (1) Ideally, the abstract would be a structured summary reflecting the purpose and content of the protocol described in the manuscript. Currently, it is a bit context-heavy and light on the information a reader might need to identify your work as a protocol that will help them do their study.

#4 (2) In addition to revising the abstract, I could also suggest editing the title to make the content more identifiable, summarising the manuscript type and key function or contribution in the title. This could perhaps be something like “A protocol for using microinjection techniques to more accurately evaluate gap junction dynamics in 3D multicellular spheroids” (though you are the experts).

#7 We would ideally like to see a complete disclosure of interests for each submitting author as per our [declaration of interests form](#).

Structured Evaluation

Editorial note: For EBT, the goal of methods paper is to provide documentation that supports the reproducibility of a method for achieving a research objective, and/or supports the process for planning a study or other research process that uses the described method.

KEY: R = Revisions recommended. N = No issues identified at this time. X = Not applicable.

Domain	1. Objectives, context, and purpose of methodology
Compliance	Important issues identified ▾ that should be addressed prior to peer-review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R ▾ Clarity about the goals or research objectives which the method is supporting N ▾ Justification for providing the method R ▾ Relation to existing templates, workflows, checklists, standards, and practices X ▾ Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	<p>1. As an editor (though not a topic expert) it seems this protocol is a potentially useful contribution to the literature and I can broadly see what it is adding in relation to existing approaches. However, to have the fullest impact on the reader, it may help to revise the introduction for clarity and add some additional sections to the manuscript (more comments on the latter in later sections).</p> <p>2. As I understand it, there are three concepts (in vitro research, cancer models, and gap junctions) core to explaining what the author’s method is for. Overall, I get what the authors are doing, but the information is somewhat jumbled and the case for the protocol could be more precisely articulated. I would suggest explaining more clearly: (a) what the state-of-the-art is for the in vitro models of cancer studies (i.e. the 2D approaches against which spheroids have certain advantages); (b) provide more</p>

	<p>detail on gap junctions and cell-to-cell communication, and why the dynamics of these are better modelled using 3D spheroids; and (c) make it clearer what the challenge is in evaluating gap junction dynamics that your specific microinjection approach addresses.</p> <p>2.1 One illustrative example of the above is at line 53, where the authors state there is “a critical gap in our current experimental capabilities”, but do not really explain what this gap is.</p> <p>3. In several places, especially the abstract, the authors refer to “this study”. However, the authors are not presenting a study but a bench protocol. The authors should be much clearer about the manuscript type they are presenting, and formulate their objectives statements and other relevant statements accordingly. (For example, at line 71 the authors say their paper “will discuss the application (etc.)” but it does not discuss the method, it presents it for other researchers to use as well. This is a perfectly valid contribution, but the type of contribution it is should be unambiguous to the reader.</p>
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Domain	2. Soundness and clarity of described methodological approach
Compliance	Important issues identified ▾ that should be addressed prior to peer-review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N ▾ Clarity about each of the individual steps being undertaken R ▾ Fit of each step in the broader, overarching process N ▾ Well-matched to stated purpose N ▾ Method can reasonably be expected to result in achieving supported goals R ▾ Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	<p>1. It could well be that I am missing something, but I think the fit between the proposed method and the assessment of gap junction functionality could be further developed to the benefit of the reader. I understand this is to do with direct observation of uptake of molecules, but the authors don't really make it explicit how their injection method supports this experimental goal (it may be as simple as dye being where it needs to be, i.e. inside an undisrupted spheroid, but I don't see this being made explicit?).</p> <p>2. I won't comment on the clarity of the individual steps and whether the method will achieve its stated goals. Peer-reviewers with direct experience of this type of work should comment on this rather than me.</p> <p>3. I think the manuscript could benefit from a discussion section. Are there any issues a prospective user of the process should in particular be aware of, that might be especially challenging or involve any “secret sauce” elements that are difficult to capture in a sequence of steps but could impact the success of the process? Are there any areas for further development? Limitations in the approach?</p>

Domain	3. Completeness of data analysis procedures
Compliance	No issues identified during editorial review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X ▾ Approach to data normalisation and cleansing techniques X ▾ Appropriate analysis pipelines (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) X ▾ Approach to summarisation and visualisation of results X ▾ Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	1. There is no data analysis component of the proposed method, so this section is not relevant.

Domain	4. Transparency and technical reproducibility
Compliance	No issues identified during editorial review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N ▾ Sufficient information provided to enable general reproducibility of approach N ▾ Appropriate balance between specificity and generality for stated purpose X ▾ Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3)* X ▾ Provision of code, data, and materials for replication (TOP 2,3,4 - L2) X ▾ Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) X ▾ Other (please explain in comments) <p>*Parentheses indicate EBT's implementation of TOP guidelines. More information here.</p>
Comments	1. No comments.

Domain	5. Community support and buy-in, versioning
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified ▾ that should be addressed prior to peer-review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N ▾ Evidence or argument for existence of community that will use technique N ▾ Comprehensibility or accessibility to prospective users R ▾ Sufficiently supported by well-annotated examples R ▾ Independent versionable location of procedure to allow updating
Comments	<p>1. It could be helpful for the authors to provide annotated examples of use of the protocol (or if not annotated, then at least some examples of when the protocol has been successfully implemented). This could be a subsection of the discussion I recommended, with annotations covering areas where the authors had to pay particular attention to one or more steps in the process.</p> <p>2. I would recommend that, alongside the manuscript, the authors post an updatable “living” version of the protocol that they can reference, so that if modifications are made in future, the reader of this manuscript can go to a more up-to-date source. This might be a record on protocols.io or an updatable version on a preprint repository.</p>

Additional comments and suggestions for revision

1. In figures, pointed arrows tend to indicate a specific location. When indicating the spheroid it may be better to use an open bracketed indicator, to distinguish the general area of the spheroid from the specific locations of the site of injection and micropipette needle.

Questionnaire adapted from [Center for Open Science form for evaluation of preregistration templates](#). Paul Whaley (Editor-in-Chief, Evidence-Based Toxicology) is a member of the COS Preregistration Templates Working Group.